

**Trends in Elderly (65+ Years)
Labor Force Participation Across
Ten OECD Countries Between (2000–2023)**

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Abstract

In the coming decades, the world will witness a rise in the elderly population share i.e. people aged 65+ years. Simultaneously there will be a shrinking working population (individuals aged between 18-64 years) due to low fertility and increased life expectancy. In such a case, the role of the elderly is being redefined in the workforce. Traditionally, that age cohort has been considered “retired” and economically inactive but that line is blurring. This study explores trends in elderly labor force participation rates (LFPR) across ten OECD countries including- Canada, Chile, Colombia, Germany, Israel, Japan, South Korea, Mexico, the United Kingdom, and the United States, between 2000 and 2023. Using quantitative analysis and secondary datasets, the paper studies changes in elderly LFPR over time, explores absolute and relative participation rates, and examines the influence of national policy interventions, pension structures, and economic conditions.

The findings reveal a general upward trend in elderly LFPR, but population growth is not directly linked to higher elderly workforce participation in all countries. There are variations across countries depending on demographic transitions phase, retirement policy reforms, pension adequacy, and cultural or economic drivers. It concludes that elderly workforce participation is not only a demographic response but also a function of targeted policy design.

Introduction

The global population is predicted to continue rising in the 21st century. It will peak during the mid 2080s to about 10.3 billion before gradually declining in 2100 to 10.2 billion, according to the United Nations. Currently, it stands at 8.2 billion. While the total population will continue to rise, the distribution of increment across different age cohorts varies significantly.

The working age population (i.e., people aged between 15-64 years capable of participating in the workforce whether currently employed or not) comprises 65% of the total global population, according to the World Bank in 2024. Of this, the labor force participation rate is around 60.8%.

Our world’s demography is at the cusp of an impending transition characterized by a rise in the elderly population share i.e., people aged 65 years or above. By 2050, their number is projected to double to 1.6 billion, representing nearly 16% of the global population (UN Population Division, 2022). Simultaneously, the working-age population is likely to decline, or plateau, in many countries. Such a phenomenon is

expected to result in potential labor shortages and increased economic dependency ratios.

The numbers and pace vary by region. But the trend is expected to unfold, sooner or later, in all economies. It is most pronounced in the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) countries, where the population is aging rapidly. On an average, 18.24% of the population in OECD nations is over 65 as of 2023. Some countries have an even higher share who are leading the trend. For example- Japan (29%), Italy (24%), and Germany (22%). (OECD, 2024)

If the dependent population rises with a low replacement level, there is a shrunken workforce available to meet the demand and supplies of the economy. It poses a potential risk to a country's ability to sustain growth and also replace the workforce with younger ones.

As a response to such challenges, elderly labor force participation rate (LFPR), defined as the percentage of people aged 65 years or above who remain employed or are actively seeking work, has gained significant research and policy attention. Prolonging participation in the workforce is increasingly viewed as a strategy to meet the effects of the shrinking labor base.

Elderly LFP trends analysis gives some insights into how different countries are tackling demographic change. In 2000, the average participation rate by the elderly in OECD economies was approximately 10.8%. In 2023, it rose to 16.3%, with notable variations across countries and regions. (OECD, 2023)

This paper explores labor force participation trends by the 65 years and above cohort across ten OECD countries, between 2000-2023. By analysing patterns and policy changes, it aims to understand how countries vary in the elderly LFPR and what role policy or other interrelated factors play in it.

Research Question

How has the elderly labor force participation in ten OECD countries changed between 2000 to 2023, and has policy played a role in influencing these trends?

- Which countries show the maximum increase and decline?
- How do policy changes correlate with elderly LFP?
- Do changes in population size impact the total elderly workforce?

Literature Review

According to the United Nations (2023), the population of 65+ year old individuals globally will exceed 2.2 billion by 2050. For the first time in human history, it will override the number of children below 18 years. The transformation is largely driven by two demographic forces: increasing life expectancy and declining fertility rates. (Leeson, 2019)

Life expectancy at birth in OECD countries has climbed steadily. In 2000, the average OECD lifespan was about mid-70 years. By 2021 it had risen to about 80 years. It can be attributed to mankind's unparalleled success in medical and technological innovations. Prevention, diagnosis and treatment of many diseases are possible now which would have been fatal in the past. In particular, OECD analyses suggest that growth in healthcare spending has directly led to longer life expectancy.

The advancement has met with a declining fertility rate. In OECD countries it has fallen from 3.3 children per woman in 1960 to just 1.5 in 2022. It is below the replacement level of 2.1. Life expectancy at birth has already increased by 10 years since 1970. (OECD, 2024).

Japan becomes a case in point where it was one of the first countries to become an "aged society" as per the UN definition. About 14% of its population had become above 65 years. In 1990, Japan experienced what was phrased the "1.57 shock", a record low fertility rate in history. In 2005, it reached 1.25. This was followed by government schemes aimed at helping couples raise children. (Haub, 2010)

Traditionally, adults above 65 have been considered "retired" and economically dependent. That boundary is now blurring as more seniors remain economically active. A shrinking working-age cohort has prompted many governments and employers to encourage delayed retirement.

Policymakers are easing obstacles to longer working lives as a response to population aging. Elderly LFPR varies widely across countries. It reflects different cultural, economic, and policy contexts. On a policy level, it has resulted in measures such as increasing retirement age, phased pensions and promoting hiring of older workers. Many advanced economies face fiscal pressure on pension systems too. (OECD, 2019).

The increasing cohort of elderly workers are emerging as a critical determinant of labor markets' dynamics. East Asian economies like Japan and South Korea are consistently ahead of the curve of senior workforce participation. In these countries,

around 13–14% of the total labor force is age 65+, which is the highest share in the OECD. (World Economic Forum, 2023)

Therefore, retaining and rejoining the elderly in the workforce in part was driven by the aging population. South Korea followed Japan closely. Its elderly population began rising sharply in the late 1990s. Percentage of 65+ year Koreans doubled from 7% in 2000 to 14% in 2019– one of the fastest growing trajectories. (Leiden Asia Centre, n.d.) Research suggests that accelerated aging and migration of younger people (especially in rural areas) was a major cause of increased elderly LFPR. (Lee, 2009).

Economic necessity is also a driving factor behind increased elderly LFPR. Comparative studies show that elderly LFP tend to remain high when pension coverage is low. Thus many seniors must keep working out of necessity. A case in point is Mexico. A review of its aging labor market notes- "*high labor force participation of elderly, and the lack of retirement pensions...the availability of a retirement pension (after contributions to a pension plan earlier in their life) reduces participation.*" (Gameren, 2010). According to few sources, older Mexicans work longer than their OECD peers largely due to the country's massive informal economy and high elderly poverty rates.

Similarly in Colombia, formal pension coverage has been historically low. Recent estimates suggest that only 26% of Colombians after retirement received pensions. This leaves the majority of seniors reliant on work or family support. Both countries have large informal sectors that play a role. Elderly people who spent the majority of their careers in informal or rural work often lack contributory pensions. Thus, they continue to work through old age out of necessity. (FP Analytics, 2019)

In the early 20th century too, work force participation among older adults was high. For instance, in 1890, about 75% of American men aged 65+ were engaged in some occupations. However, this figure declined significantly over the coming decades and dropped to about 40% by 1950 followed by 20% by the late 20th century. (Pope & Wimmer, 1998)

Several factors contributed to this decline:

- **Introduction of Social Security:** The establishment of Social Security in the 1930s provided financial support, reducing the necessity for older individuals to remain in the workforce.

- **Pension Plans:** The growth of employer-sponsored pension plans offered additional retirement security.
- **Economic Prosperity:** Post-World War II economic growth allowed for earlier retirement.

In recent years, the shift from secure pensions to individual 401(k) plans in the U.S., in addition to insufficient savings and high cost of living has left many older adults unprepared for retirement. Surveys find that a large share of seniors continue working due to inadequate retirement funds or lack of reliable employer-sponsored pensions. (Investopedia, 2025)

Financial pressures further influence senior work patterns. The 2008 global financial crisis caused job insecurity for older workers (Bodnar & Nerlich, 2020) In several countries, people lost retirement savings and it even pushed some seniors to work longer due to financial necessity. (National Research Council, 2012).

More recently, the COVID-19 pandemic posed new challenges. Many elderly people ended up retiring due to health risks, potentially slowing gains in the elder labor force. Specifically, there was a 6.7 percentage point rise in the probability of leaving employment, representing a 43% increase over pre-pandemic levels. Notably, this surge in job exits did not correspond with a proportional increase in retirements, suggesting that many older individuals left the workforce without formally retiring.

Despite these sporadic shocks, the larger trend has been upward in elderly LFP%, perhaps driven by changing policy and economic forces. (Bodnar & Nerlich, 2020)

Later work life behavior is also shaped by the country's pension system design. Notably, most EU and OECD governments have legislated gradual increases in the statutory retirement age. Along with it, conditions for early exit from the labor force are tightened. (Eiffe et al.,2025)

Germany's population declined from ~82.5 million in 2004 to ~80.4 million in 2012 due to low fertility (1.3–1.4 children per woman) and negative natural increase. This means that deaths have outpaced births annually since 1972 (PRB, 2011; Destatis, 2022). Despite immigration, net migration gains during this period were modest. (UN DESA, 2019).

Simultaneously, many efforts were made by the government to reshape retirement trends. It included phasing out early retirement options by 2005 and increasing the statutory retirement age from 65 to 67, initiated in 2012 (Börsch-Supan et al., 2013; Walwei & Deller, 2021). Adding to it were the pension bonuses for delayed

retirement and tax-sheltered “mini-jobs” introduced around 2003 that encouraged prolonged employment among elders (Anger et al., 2018).

Germany thus demonstrates how aging societies can leverage policy to extend workforce participation despite demographic contraction.

Many scholarly contributions collectively challenge a one-dimensional narrative too. Demographic aging and policy reforms (e.g., retirement age increases) are often cited as primary drivers of elderly LFP. But a broader literature points to cultural context, family roles, labor demand etc.

Harris (2021) highlights that age preference in hiring plays a key role in reducing elderly LFP in the U.S. Biased hiring and retention practices reduce employer demand and also discourage seniors from seeking jobs, pushing many capable workers out of the labor market. Even in the UK, ageist stereotypes reduce recruitment of older workers. (KCL, 2024)

Employer practices can also affect participation. In many European countries, measures like flexible hours, retraining, and ergonomic adjustments help retain older workers. (Eiffe & Weber, 2024)

Additionally, many older adults, especially in low-income countries, work informally due to limited pension access. In such contexts, legal retirement ages have limited real-world impact. Even in wealthier countries, some seniors continue gig or cash work, often unrecorded in official statistics. (Henry & Golman, 2021)

Personal preferences also shape retirement decisions. Studies show that psychological burnout and the desire for leisure can sometimes outweigh financial factors. Contrastingly, some seniors remain employed for social engagement, underscoring the importance of individual motivation (Knoll, 2011) Senior labor participation, therefore, reflects a complex mix of structural, economic, social, and personal factors. Together, these findings challenge simplistic narratives linking aging and retirement policy to senior LFP.

Existing research serves as an important foundation for the understanding of demographic changes’ implications. However, every country may have a different social, cultural and political landscape in terms of elderly LFPR. Studying literature in depth for some countries sets a foundation to understanding context for different countries’ responses. It is also important for policy shaping and reform work. This study integrates both relative and absolute metrics of labor force participation. It aims to offer descriptive insights into how national policy approaches may be influencing workforce retention among older adults.

Methodology

The study adopts a quantitative analysis of LFP trends among people aged 65+ years in select OECD countries between 2000-2023. For analyzing participation trends in specific countries, it uses secondary research.

The objective was to observe trends in the last two decades, compare relative and absolute participation rates, and derive policy-relevant insights.

Sample Selection

Ten OECD countries' data was studied and analysed: Canada, Chile, Colombia, Germany, Israel, Japan, South Korea, Mexico, the United Kingdom, and the United States. These countries were selected based on the availability of complete, reliable data from credible sources ([OECD](#) and [Statista](#)).

Additionally, the sample provides a geographically and economically diverse group. It includes countries from developed regions (such as Europe and the United States from North America), and also developing economies (such as Chile, Mexico etc.) This diversity provides space to explore varied pension systems, population structures and demographic phases.

Data Sources

Publicly available secondary data sources were used while ensuring credibility. From there, the selected countries' data on annual labor force participation rate and annual population estimates between 2000-2023 were extracted.

- **[OECD Labor Force Statistics](#)**: Annual labor force participation rates among people aged 65+ for each country from 2000-2023.
- **Statista**: Annual population of each country from 2000 to 2023.

Variables

- **Dependent Variable**: Labor force participation rate (%) for people aged 65+.
- **Independent Variable**: Country and year.
- **Derived Variable**: Estimated number of elderly workers = (LFP% * total population).

Data Cleaning and Preparation

The extracted data was cleaned and then processed using Google Sheets:

1. Standardized to long format: Country – Year – Value.
2. Merged datasets on country-year keys using VLOOKUP.
3. Calculated estimated elderly workers using a derived formula i.e., LFP% × total population.

Tools and Software

Google Sheets: Used for cleaning, merging, calculations, basic charting and visualization.

The full dataset is available [here](#). [Click to view]

Analytical Approach

A visual analysis was done to study the data in different contexts including-

- Time series plots (line graphs) to show LFP% over time
- Bar and slope charts for changes between 2000 and 2023
- Heatmaps for identifying high/low participation countries and YoY analysis
- Bubble chart for comparing LFP% vs. population size

Some country-specific labor and retirement policy changes were examined using secondary literature. These helped interpret and attribute deviations in trends, outliers, and clusters in a policy context.

Ethical Considerations

The study uses publicly available datasets and does not involve human subjects. As such, no institutional ethical approval was required.

Results/Findings

The aim of the study was to investigate how elderly LFPR has evolved across ten OECD countries between 2000 and 2023. Specifically, it aimed to answer: **Which countries have experienced the significant changes in elderly LFP, and what demographic or policy factors may explain these trends?**

The following results are derived from both percentage and absolute comparisons. It aims to highlight patterns of older adults' participation in the workforce and how the share has changed over time in context of every country's broader population.

The analysis further sheds light on relevant social factors, varying policy approaches etc. to interpret and attribute deviations in trends, outliers, and clusters.

Elderly Labor Force Participation Trends 2000 vs. 2023

A general upward trend in elderly LFP rates was observed in all countries except Mexico and Colombia. The increase was maximum in Germany (from 2.66% in 2000 to 9.08% in 2023), Canada (from 5.99% in 2000 to 14.92% in 2023) and Israel (from 9.25% in 2000 to 21.67% in 2023).

Fig 1. Growth line of elderly LFPR from 2000-2023

Countries such as Japan, South Korea, Mexico and Colombia observed high participation since the start of the 21st century, and continued to remain above average from other countries in 2023. Despite witnessing a reduction in ELFP rates in the same year, Colombia and Mexico have above average participation rates.

South Korea had the highest participation rate at 38.33% in 2023. By contrast, Germany had the lowest at 9.08%. Yet, Germany had tripled its participation rate from 2.66% to 9.08%. And South Korea has increased by only 9%.

Fig.2 Elderly Labor Force Participation Trends 2000 vs. 2023

Elderly Workforce Participation in 2023

Since population varies across all the OECD countries, the actual number of elderly people in the workforce is different. It depicts a very different trend of participation.

While South Korea had the highest participation rate at 38.33% in 2023, the United States had the highest number of elderly workers at 660 million, which is just 12.88% of their population. In the same year, Israel had 2 million people, the lowest number of elderly individuals in the workforce. It is evident that a country's population size, not just LFP%, contributes to the scale of elderly workforce involvement.

Fig 3. Estimated elderly workers in 2023

LFP% vs. Population Size

A scatter plot was created to explore a potential correlation between higher national populations corresponding with higher elderly LFP%. No strong correlation was found.

South Korea and Colombia had almost the same population, ~51.7 million and ~52.3 million respectively. Yet, there was a 14% difference in elderly labor force participation, with South Korea at 38.33% and Colombia at 24.55%

South Korea consistently had one of the highest elderly LFP% throughout the 23 years but the population remained mid-sized.

Similarly, the U.S., with a lower participation rate had the highest number of elderly workers due to its larger population in 2023.

Fig. 4 Population vs LFP rate

Year-on-Year Patterns (Heatmap)

To observe micro trends and YoY changes, a heatmap was created with darker shade of green implying higher participation rate.

Overall, the total LFP% (sum of all ten OECD countries) grew from 165.87% in 2000 to 211.95% in 2023. It counts for a net increase of +46.08%.

The darker shades of green (higher LFP%) are clearly concentrated in Mexico, Colombia, South Korea, while lighter hues dominate Germany and the UK.

Countries like the UK, Germany and Canada started from low bases but have shown significant growth between 2000-2023. South Korea and Japan started with a high base and continued to grow.

The highest YoY spike in elderly LFP% was seen in Israel between 2011-2012. It increased by 2.46%, from 14.24% to 16.70%.

This was followed by Chile, which experienced a sharp increase of 1.96%, jumping from 19.57% to 21.53% over the same period (2011-2012).

Colombia saw a pronounced change in elderly labor force participation twice among the ten countries. Between 2007-2008, the participation rate increased by 2.91% to 27.10% from 24.19%. Then, between 2019-2020, a major dip occurred in most countries, In Colombia, the country saw elderly LFP fall to 21.16% from 25.29%.

Country	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Canada	9.39	9.23	9.17	7.47	7.43	6.71	6.29	6.74	6.89	6.68	11.26	11.71	12.36	13.05	13.28	13.24	13.92	14.05	14.14	14.87	14.96	14.87	14.87	14.87
Chile	17.32	18.26	15.57	18.70	17.08	18.09	18.00	19.27	19.81	18.80	19.97	21.53	21.33	21.92	22.75	23.69	24.73	24.90	24.68	25.20	18.09	18.16	19.58	21.10
Colombia	9.23	10.80	10.66	10.62	10.66	10.66	10.66	10.66	10.66	10.66	10.66	10.66	10.66	10.66	10.66	10.66	10.66	10.66	10.66	10.66	10.66	10.66	10.66	10.66
Germany	2.66	2.64	2.65	2.61	2.60	2.40	2.47	2.72	2.66	2.69	4.05	4.02	4.07	4.44	4.44	4.81	4.80	4.81	7.03	7.05	7.04	7.03	7.02	8.47
Israel	3.23	3.27	3.21	3.11	3.14	3.14	3.14	3.14	3.14	3.14	3.14	3.14	3.14	3.14	3.14	3.14	3.14	3.14	3.14	3.14	3.14	3.14	3.14	3.14
Japan	22.61	21.76	20.81	20.19	19.77	19.78	19.81	20.14	20.18	20.26	19.90	19.89	19.84	20.55	21.27	22.11	22.76	23.47	24.48	25.32	25.48	25.99	25.61	25.16
Mexico	30.61	29.21	28.12	28.68	28.61	28.71	28.48	28.48	28.48	27.97	27.70	28.87	27.72	28.84	28.86	27.76	28.53	27.16	28.96	24.11	22.69	24.61	23.64	23.64
South Korea	26.57	26.69	26.41	26.64	26.41	26.41	26.41	26.41	26.41	26.41	26.41	26.41	26.41	26.41	26.41	26.41	26.41	26.41	26.41	26.41	26.41	26.41	26.41	26.41
United Kingdom	2.27	4.27	5.49	5.49	6.17	6.28	6.78	7.22	7.29	7.79	8.20	8.62	9.00	9.64	10.24	10.69	10.54	10.43	10.65	10.51	10.76	10.42	11.07	11.52
United States	12.88	13.01	13.22	13.69	14.44	15.24	16.40	16.62	16.80	17.20	17.30	17.90	18.68	18.70	18.99	18.93	19.30	19.33	19.96	20.79	19.44	18.86	18.21	18.22

Fig. 5 Full-resolution version of the heatmap is available [here](#).

Absolute number of elderly LFP

All the ten OECD countries showed an upward trend in the absolute number of elderly workers in the 23 year period. The sum total of elderly workers was ~131 million in 2000, which rose to ~192 million in 2023, accounting for a 47% increase.

In particular, the United States contributed to the largest share of the total increase in elderly workforce participation. It increased from about ~36.3 million (2000) to ~66 million in 2023.

Almost all countries saw a dip from 2019-2020, even if it was minor. The dip was more pronounced in Chile ~4.8 million in 2019 to ~3.6 million in 2020; Colombia ~12.6 million in 2019 to ~10.7 million in 2020; and Mexico ~33 million in 2019 to ~30 million in 2020.

Only Japan and South Korea saw modest increases between 2019-2020.

Fig. 6 Growth in estimated total number of elderly workers between 2000-2023

Discussion

It is thus evident that elderly labor force participation has had an upward trend in the 23 years between 2000-2023, across the selected ten OECD countries. Since all economies are in varying demographic transition stages, the participation levels and the factors determining it remain different.

Our analysis over the selected time period found no strong correlation between increasing population and elderly labor force participation. As discussed in the literature review, the UN projects that the world's population will continue to grow, reaching a peak of around 10.4 billion in the mid-2080s (United Nations, 2022).

A contributing factor, particularly in OECD countries and also in the rest of the world, is increased life expectancy attributed to medical advancements and technological innovations. In OECD countries, life expectancy at birth has gone up from mid-70s in the early 2000s to about 80 years in the early 2020s. (OECD, 2023). However, even though the population has risen across many of the ten countries over 23 years, it has not translated or reflected in a proportional increased participation of the elderly workforce.

For instance, in Chile, the population increased by +180,229 in 2001 from 2000, but the elderly labor force participation rate declined by 1.06%. Similarly in Canada in 2020, the population increased by +388,967 from 2019, but the elderly labor force participation rate decreased by 0.92%.

Further, in 2023, South Korea and Colombia had almost the same population ~51.7 million and ~52.3 million respectively. Yet, there was a 14% difference in elderly labor force participation, with South Korea at 38.33% and Colombia at 24.55%.

Similarly, despite Israel having the lowest total population, approximately 9.26 million, it had a high elderly LFPR at 21.665%. Interestingly, Chile, with a significantly larger population of around 19.65 million, shares the exact same elderly LFP% of 21.665%. This similarity suggests that factors beyond population size such as social policy, pension design, labor market conditions, and cultural attitudes toward aging may play a more pivotal role in shaping elderly workforce participation.

Some countries have witnessed high elderly LFPR at the start of the century. In particular, Mexico (30.61%), followed by Colombia (29.7%), South Korea (29.57%) and Japan (22.61%). As observed in the literature review, higher elderly LFPR around 2000 was generally observed in countries where: (1) population aging hit early and hard and pressured labor markets (as in Japan, Korea) and/or (2) pension and welfare systems were less developed along with high level of informal work which forced elders to work longer as a necessity (as in Mexico, Colombia, Chile)

For instance, In Japan, the participation rate was at 22.61% in 2000. In the previous decade it witnessed an unprecedented decline in fertility rates while becoming an aged nation, as per the UN definition (Haub, 2010). Hence, the high participation rate can be attributed to these demographic factors.

In short, when the elderly population surged, these societies responded by retaining older adults in the workforce. It contrasts with western countries that did not face acute aging until later and initially (i.e. around the 2000s) had lower senior LFPR. Eg: Germany.

South Korea had the highest participation rate at 38.33% in 2023, which is up from 29.57% in 2000. It had the highest elderly labor force participation rates in 2023. By contrast Germany had the lowest rate in 2023 at 9.08%, but it was a triple jump from 2.66% in 2000.

Germany saw a declining population between 2004-2012. In the same period, there was a sustained increase in the elderly labor force participation rate.

Shrinking working-age cohorts prompts governments to encourage delayed retirements. In many advanced economies, longer working lives are a response to population aging. (OECD, 2019). Changes to retirement age, pension incentives and labor shortages drive an increased labor participation by the elderly. The trend is consistent with the findings from Eiffe et al. (2025) who observe policy reforms across OECD and EU nations to prolong working lives.

The number of senior workers in Germany swelled from ~2.2 million in 2000 to ~7.7 million in 2023, which is a ~5.5 million increase. Existing literature's findings can be attributed to this increase. It observes that Germany has "caught up considerably" in older people's employment in recent decades. However, its elderly LFPR remains below the OECD average. (Walwei, 2024)

By contrast the UK, another European OECD country, already had a moderate rate of participation at 5.57% in 2000. Then, it saw a steady, continuous rise. Key drivers are likely to be the increase in state pension ages, notably for women, from 60-65 between 2010-2018 and then to 66 by 2020. It was followed by the abolition of the Default Retirement Age in 2011 which ended forced retirement at 65. (The Guardian, 2011) These changes enabled or encouraged more seniors to remain employed or return to the workforce. In fact, the total number of elderly workers increased more than twice over the 23 years, from ~3.1 million to ~7.9 million.

Clearly, Germany's senior participation tripled in relative terms, while the UK's doubled, reflecting a major shift toward later-life employment in both countries. But both the countries should be viewed in a larger European policy context. These

results reinforce the notion of a widespread shift toward extended working lives in Europe. The UK and Germany, in line with European peers, have seen older adults' employment increase substantially, reflecting policy efforts to encourage later retirement. (Eiffe, Muller, & Weber, 2024)

Within the EU countries, Germany's demographic and labor participation trajectory between 2004-2012 presents a paradox— a declining population alongside a rising elderly LFPR. This is well-documented in literature linking long-term demographic decline with delayed retirement reforms.

These structural reforms were complemented by the Hartz IV labor market reforms (2005), which tightened unemployment benefits and promoted part-time and senior employment (Dietz & Walwei, 2011). Together with improvements in health, education levels, and employer age-friendly policies, they helped Germany reverse a long-standing trend of early labor market exit among older workers (Steiner, 2017; Intereconomics, 2021).

Contrasting to Japan, Mexico, South Korea and Colombia's high starting base in 2000, Germany's was the lowest. Their early retirement policies, implemented from the 1970s onward, were made in an attempt to make more room for their then booming working age cohort. Consequently, it encouraged workers to exit the labor market well before the official retirement age of 65 as was the intention of these policies.

It was accelerated by generous public pension schemes that allowed retirement at as early as 60 years. These policies, including provisions for unemployment and disability pensions, led to an exceptionally low effective retirement age, with many workers retiring by age 60–63. As a result, in 2000, Germany had one of the lowest elderly LFPR among OECD countries.

Between 2019-2020, all countries except South Korea and Japan saw a dip in the total number of elderly individuals in the workforce. It can be attributed to the COVID-19 pandemic that altered participation rates significantly, driven by a surge in job exits. (Owen et al, 2023).

In Chile, the dip was more pronounced. It had ~4.8 million elderly workers in 2019 which fell to ~3.6 million in 2020; Colombia went from ~12.6 million in 2019 to ~10.7 million in 2020; and Mexico from ~33 million in 2019 to ~30 million in 2020.

Clearly the elderly labor force participation rate is susceptible to other factors such as economic conditions or even health emergencies, and are not solely a reflection of the demographic phase the country is in.

While the majority of the countries saw the participation rate go upwards, Mexico and Colombia stand out due to declining trends. It went from 31% to 26% in Mexico, and 30% to 24.5% in Colombia. A key factor here is the introduction of non-contributory pension programs that enabled many elderly people to stop working. Mexico implemented what was called the "70 y Más" old-age benefit in 2007 (later expanded to cover age 65+ nationally), providing a basic pension to seniors with no formal coverage. It ties back to the literature by Gamreen (2010) which suggested that the availability of pension reduces participation in the labor force by the elderly population. Thus, while the reduction in social security benefits prolongs working life, the opposite is also true.

In the case of Colombia, economic growth and poverty reduction eased the pressure on elderly people to remain employed as seen through literature review.

To address these issues and mitigate old-age poverty, the Colombian government has implemented supplementary measures, including the Beneficios Económicos Periódicos (BEPS) scheme. This matching-contribution program targets informal workers and near-retirement individuals with insufficient contributions for a standard pension. Additionally, the government has expanded the coverage of its non-contributory old-age income support programs. However, this has come at the expense of further reducing already modest benefit levels. (OECD, 2015)

These incremental reforms have helped extend basic income support to a larger segment of the elderly population, thereby easing the economic necessity for continued employment among older Colombians. As such, they have likely contributed to the observed decline in elderly labor force participation between 2000 and 2023.

The Colombian case exemplifies a broader Latin American trend where better health and longer lives have not led to longer working lives, because improved pension coverage has made earlier retirement a viable and attractive option. (NIUSSP, 2018).

In South Korea, the largest net increase was observed with +8.7%. It can be attributed to the literature on trends of policy changes in retirement age and post-crisis economic vulnerability (Choi & Park, 2020; OECD, 2022).

A notable acceleration in elderly LFPR occurred between 2010 and 2020 in Israel. This speed was greater than what it had observed in the previous decade i.e. from 2000-2010. This trend is clearly reflected in the heatmap visualization and suggests a structural inflection point when compared to the more gradual increases seen in the 2000s.

Key drivers include pension and retirement age reforms in the 2000s, which raised the eligibility age for pensions and mandatory retirement from 65 to 67 for both men and women. Additionally, Israel's relatively modest pension system, which has created a financial incentive for seniors to continue working, further supported this trend. As a result, by the late 2010s, Israel's 65+ LFPR (around 20% or higher) These baseline differences in 2000 also foreshadowed divergent policy priorities in the ensuing decades. Countries like Japan and South Korea, faced with rapidly aging populations, focused on policy innovation to extend working life – raising mandatory retirement ages, promoting senior employment programs etc.

In contrast, countries such as Mexico and Colombia prioritized expanding old-age income support (e.g. non-contributory pensions like Colombia Mayor or Mexico's 70+y pension) to reduce poverty among those working out of necessity. Chile, which had implemented a privatized pension system, discovered gaps in benefit adequacy and also introduced supplements to prevent elderly poverty, even as it encourages active aging initiatives.

In this study, a limitation was the relatively small sample size, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to larger populations. Additionally, the data collection was confined to a single region, which may not fully reflect broader trends or variations in other geographical locations. While efforts were made to ensure the accuracy of the measurement tools, the possibility of a certain degree of subjectivity in the data interpretation could not be entirely ruled out, which might introduce bias. Future research could benefit from expanding the sample size and including diverse geographic areas to enhance the applicability of the results.

Conclusion

Based on the data analysed for over 20+ years, it is established that elderly labor force participation in the ten OECD countries see a gradual, upward trend overall. But the changes are susceptible to many catalysts. These include financial conditions of the economy, health emergencies and also the demographic transition phase the country is undergoing.

This study conducted systematic literature review to understand population forecasts and general trends expected in the coming decades. Further, it narrowed down the scope to a diverse group of randomly selected ten OECD countries to study macro changes.

Evidence from previous study indicates that an aging population, rising demographic dividend and the resultant shrinking labor force is the reason behind

policy-level efforts of prolonging labor force participation. Moreover, the research highlighted that while it may seem that a rising population would equate to a rise in elderly labor force participation, there cannot be established a positive correlation between the two.

A deeper study of the individual countries policies could be attributed to sudden drops or spikes in the YoY elderly labor force participation, and also the trend as a whole.

These findings should be interpreted with caution as there were limitations in the research. Random ten countries were selected and may not represent the trends in the whole of the OECD. Further, the population count and elderly labor force participation rates began with the year 2000 as the base. The research did not delve into the previous decades' changes or population policy landscape that might account for or affect the participation in the year after. Data was studied for ten OECD countries due to availability and credibility. It may not be sufficient to account for population trends in other economic regions.

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